
**Co-developing desired visions for lake futures:
A PLURALAKES facilitation guide**

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For more information, please visit the [PLURALAKES website](#).

PLURALAKES visioning workshops: Summary

Background and approach

PLURALAKES is an international [Water4All](#) research project working to incorporate plural values of lakes into governance for sustainable and just lake futures. PLURALAKES is a transdisciplinary research project, with an international, interdisciplinary team that has expertise spanning freshwater ecology, environmental economics, governance, ecosystem modelling, and futures thinking.

Using the [Nature Futures Framework](#) (NFF) as a guiding tool, PLURALAKES connects participatory visioning, systems thinking, environmental valuation, and ecosystem modelling across case studies in Finland, the UK, and the Netherlands.

The aim of PLURALAKES is to co-create actionable pathways for safeguarding lake ecosystems and the communities that depend on them. To do this, we are developing and testing a novel approach to co-developing desired visions for lake futures, as well as pathways to achieving these visions.

The PLURALAKES approach includes co-developing **visions** of desired futures with local actors in each case study, then co-developing and modelling possible **pathways** to achieving these visions, and, finally, discussing the outputs of modelled and co-developed pathways with actors to identify preferred pathways. These visions and pathways will then be shared with decision makers to inform lake governance.

This facilitation guide outlines the process of the **visioning workshop**, where local actors are invited to co-develop desired visions for their case study lake(s) and surrounding watershed(s). In these workshops, the NFF is used to broaden actors' thinking about desired people-lake relations, and then the X-curve method is used to focus actors' thinking about desired people-lake relations into distinct time horizons, together with specific opportunities (or seeds) and barriers to achieving these visions.

Reflections and lessons learned

To date, PLURALAKES has facilitated two visioning workshops using this guide. The first was held in the English Lake District in the United Kingdom on May 20, 2025. This workshop followed the timeline provided in this guide, lasting from 9:30–15:30 (6 hours total, including a 50min lunch break). In this workshop, groups were formed based on where people physically positioned themselves according to the NFF value perspectives, so that groups were comprised of people who positioned themselves similarly along the value perspectives. A full report on this workshop is available [here](#).

The second workshop was held in Ilomantsi in Eastern Finland on September 25, 2025. This workshop was shorter, lasting from 14:30–18:15 (just under 4 hours with no breaks). In addition to being shorter by about an hour, groups were intentionally formed to separate individuals who had previously worked together or knew each other to increase opportunities to introduce diversity in opinions. Aside from these differences, both workshops were conducted according to this guide.

After each workshop, we evaluated participant experiences using a survey. Using insights from these post-workshop surveys, we share some initial lessons learned through facilitating these two workshops.

In the English Lake District, initial lessons learned include:

- **Build in time for sharing visions amongst groups:** we received feedback that participants were interested in hearing the visions of other groups at the end of the workshop, but in this workshop, we ran short on time.
- **Greater clarity on how seeds can be connected to visions:** Some participants felt confused at how to connect seeds to future outcomes. More time spent on explaining the X-curve, or perhaps providing examples, could help.
- **Diverse perspectives are needed.** Although several workshop participants reported that they found it energizing to hear from others who were passionate about lakes in the English Lake District and who also desired change, they felt that diverse perspectives were necessary to affect this change.

In the Finnish case study, we learned:

- **Better representation by locals and industry are needed.** In the Finnish case study, only two workshop participants were local to the region, and none represented the local industry. Because of this, workshop participants felt that diverse perspectives were missing from the discussion.
 - Additionally, perhaps related to the workshop participants not being local to the region, when asked whether they felt more confident discussing or influencing the future of the lake in the Finnish case study, most workshop participants felt they either did not feel more confident or only felt somewhat more confident discussing or influencing these issues.
- **Simplify, where possible, the instructions for each round:** Some participants felt that there were too many questions asked at once. This could be related to the compressed timeline for the workshop activities. Providing more information about the workshop goals and frameworks used in the workshop to the participants prior to the workshop may help participants be more prepared. Additionally, providing a printed set of questions for participants may help them to consider the questions and follow discussions more easily.

Across both case studies, we learned:

- **The value for participants across both workshops was the opportunity to learn more about the challenges facing the lake(s), as well as from each other and their varying perspectives.** This was mentioned by 7/10 respondents in the post-workshop survey in Finland, and by 7/11 respondents in the post-workshop survey in the UK.
- **Engaging with diverse actors in the region is critical.** In both workshops, representatives from agriculture, tourism, businesses, and industry were absent, although efforts were made to include these groups in the workshops. Furthermore, community members not engaged in water-related professions, or involved in the previously noted groups, were also missing in both workshops—these groups may be lake users and have important perspectives worth including in lake visions, though more effort may be required to identify community members and invite them to the workshops. Participants noted that having these voices missing from the workshops were counterproductive to having plural values incorporated into visions and to building capacity for implementing solutions. We are working to find ways to include these groups to ensure their voices are at the table.

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1. Introduction

Workshop Objective:

This 1-day workshop introduces the creative visioning tools the PLURALAKES project will use to strengthen the integration of diverse values into lake governance in the region [**note: include name of case study location here, e.g., English Lake District/ Koitajoki-Koitere river basin**], to support thriving lakes and communities. Together, participants will 1) explore plural values and relationships with the lakes in the case study region; 2) envision the future of the lakes in the case study; 3) explore pathways to desirable futures. This is an explorative workshop, laying the foundation for follow-up research and workshops delving deeper into each of the three parts.

Programme at a glance:

09:30 – Register and refreshments

10:00 – Welcome and introduction by lead facilitator and workshop host(s)

10:30 – *Part 1 (values).*

11:00 – Coffee Break

11:20 – *Part 2 (visions).*

12:10 – Lunch

13:00 – *Part 3 (pathways).*

14:00 – Coffee Break

14:30 – *Part 4 (pathways).*

15:00 – Wrap-up discussion and next steps, workshop host(s)

15:30 – Meeting close

2. Introduction to main frameworks:

We use two frameworks to guide activities and discussions: the Nature Futures Framework, to *open-up* people's thinking about desired people-lake relations, and the X-curve, to *focus* people's thinking about desired people-lake relations into distinct time horizons and how they are connected.

Nature Futures Framework

The [Nature Futures Framework](#) (NFF) presents a triangular shape that captures diverse, positive values for human-nature relationships. It positions three main ways of relating to nature (or 'value perspectives') in the three vertices, opening up an interior space where plural values can be explored (Pereira et al., 2020).

- In the **nature for nature** perspective, people view nature as having intrinsic value, and value is placed on the diversity of species, habitats, ecosystems, and processes that form the natural world, and on nature's ability to function autonomously.
- The **nature for society** perspective highlights the utilitarian benefits and instrumental values that nature provides to people and societies.
- The **nature as culture/one with nature** perspective primarily highlights relational values of nature, where societies, cultures, traditions, and faiths are intertwined with nature in shaping diverse bio-cultural landscapes.

Figure 1: The Nature Futures Framework triangle. In (PBL, 2018).

Scenarios are stories or pathways about how the future might unfold under different assumptions, decisions, or values. They can be expressed in words, numbers, or art. They don't predict the future but help us imagine what could happen and what choices might lead to different outcomes.

Models are simplified representations of systems that capture key elements and assumptions about how they interact. They help us explore how systems behave and what might happen under

different conditions. They can be used to test the logic of scenarios, estimate impacts, and understand cause–effect relationships.

The NFF is a heuristic (IPBES, 2023) designed to catalyse the development of scenarios and models that:

- Put nature and biodiversity at the centre of the storyline
- Engage with peoples' plural values of nature
- Describe desirable futures
- Engage with transformative changes required to achieve desirable futures
- Are co-produced through participatory processes

On the one hand, the framework helps surface contrasting perspectives, revealing trade-offs and tensions by showing how different value orientations can lead to very different futures for people and nature. On the other hand, it helps highlight shared values and potential synergies, pointing to interventions with co-benefits and common enabling conditions that support multiple values simultaneously. In this way, the NFF serves as a tool for inclusive dialogue, helping to navigate diverse priorities and co-create just and sustainable futures for people and the planet.

The X-curve

We will use a simplified version of the [X-curve](#), a tool for exploring how transitions unfold over time (Silvestri et al., 2022). It helps identify the envisioned future (top right) and what practices, values, or structures need to be scaled up to make it viable. At the same time, it invites reflection on what promising initiatives are emerging now and what needs to grow (bottom left); what dominant systems or practices sustain current problems (top left); and what needs to be phased out to enable the desired future (bottom right). Used together with the Nature Futures Framework, it helps connect visions to change pathways.

Figure 2: The X-curve. In (Silvestri et al., 2022)

3. Preparation

Pre-Workshop

- Reflect on researcher team's perspective on workshop exercises and questions:
 - What needs to be adapted to a) answer research questions, and b) meet transdisciplinary goals? E.g., are the terms used in this facilitation guide coherent with and translating to the concepts that you want to collect and analyze responses / data for?
- Reflect on participants' perspective on workshop exercises and questions:
 - Which pre-information is necessary so that they can participate on 'equal grounds'? E.g., concepts used during the workshop that need explanation but for which there's too little time at the workshop
 - Use this to inform pre-workshop information package and programme
- Reflect on whether note-taking formats and overall data collection (e.g. posters, illustrations, etc.) are suitable for analysis
- Send pre-workshop information package and programme. Include object homework, objectives, logistics
- Create Introduction ppt
- Order refreshments
- Select facilitators and rapporteurs
- Ensure each role is clear and people know what to do, including what is needed for data collection and analysis

Materials Checklist

- Introduction ppt
- Consent form and sign-in sheet
- 4 A0 sheets with X-curve
- Sticky notes, markers, flipcharts
- Workshop agenda (printed/displayed)
- Facilitation guide (printed)
- Nametags (optional)
- Post-survey (online)
- Rope or tape

Room Setup

- Space on the floor to create a large NFF triangle (using tape or rope)
- Four small tables or breakout spaces for group work
- Visualization wall for clustering visions

Post-Workshop

- Administer post-workshop survey to evaluate workshop experiences
 - Collect sheets with X-curves and sticky notes from each group
 - Clean up and compile notes from each group
 - Digitize sticky notes for each group
 - Report back to team and participants
-

4. Roles and Responsibilities

Lead facilitator

- Oversight, overall flow, plenary moderation
- Align with graphic artist (if present)

Group facilitator

- Guide activities and discussions. Keep time but remain adaptive.
- Ensure inclusive, safe, and productive dialogue. Promote diversity of views. Respect all contributions. Balance speaking opportunities. Uphold ethical and respectful engagement throughout.
- Encourage participants to speak from their own experience.
- Support documentation and synthesis of outcomes. Actively encourage participants to write their input on a sticky note and place it on the joint sheet.
- We don't necessarily seek consensus. We allow for plurality for a rich picture to emerge that can be unpacked later. It's fine if participants want to first discuss their input and find agreement before they add their input, but participants may also include their own ideas and preferences. If tension arises, document the tension in the middle of the x-curve.

Rapporteur

- Help ensure that verbal expressions are captured on sticky notes
 - Capture key discussion, tensions or agreements in own notebook
 - Reflections on the process, what works, what doesn't
 - Support artist in residence if they require material/input from the process
-

5. Workshop Process

Registration and refreshments (9.30 - 30 min)

- Consent form, registration, name tag

Opening (10.00 – 30 min)

- Welcome participants, introduce facilitators
- Explain PLURALAKES project and workshop objectives.
- Introduce key frameworks
- Share house rules and secure verbal agreement.

Key points to reinforce: No right or wrong answers; Listen actively and respectfully; Personal connections matter.

- (2 min) *Think of a lake in the [case study area] that holds meaning for you. What is your connection? A moment, a story, a feeling?*
 - Group introductions: share your name and in one sentence, what connection you bring.
-

Step 1 - Values, imagination and group formation (9.30 – 30 min)

Lead facilitator:

- (3 min) *“Stand or sit comfortably. Close your eyes. Take a deep breath in... and out. Now imagine it is the future — a future where your relationship with this lake has flourished and helped shape the world around it. Where are you? What do you see? What do you hear? What do you smell? What do you taste?”*
- (2 min) *“Open your eyes. Walk to the place in the NFF triangle that best represents your future vision — Nature for Nature, Nature for Society, or Nature as Culture — or somewhere in between.”*
- (8 min) *“Find someone near you. Share the story of your connection and what you envisioned. Why do you think it fits in this specific place of the NFF?”*
- (8 min) Expand the group by merging groups next to each other and continue sharing.
- Lead facilitator will help create three subgroups of 5 or 6 people.

Coffee Break (11:00 – 20 min)

- Facilitators set up the room
 - Participants continue chatting
-

Step 2 - Populating the X-curve - Desired future (11:20 – 50 min).

In subgroups.

Objective: Moving from individual perspectives to a shared plural vision situated at the top right of the X-curve (where desirable futures have taken hold and are sustained systemically).

- (5 min) Introduction by facilitator. Explain the X-curve's top right as the space of consolidated futures: values, institutions, and practices that have scales and are shaping the system. This is not about consensus but about weaving together diverse desirable elements into a pluralistic target space.
- (5 min) *"To begin building a shared future vision, start by writing down the essence of what you shared earlier — your connection to the lake and what made it meaningful. Think of it as one key element that should be present in a desirable future. Feel free to add several elements if you like".*
- (15min) *"Continue exploring what your desirable future for the [case study] lake(s) look like; What are important characteristics of the future you imagined?"*
 - *What values are expressed and sustained?*
 - *How do people live with the lake?*
 - *What are people celebrating or protecting?*
 - *What are you proud of?*
 - *What kinds of decisions are being made, and by whom?*
 - *What rules, institutions, or technologies support this way of life?*

Motivate people to write down their thoughts on sticky notes and place them in the top right corner of the X-curve. This does not need to be a specific year, as at this point, we don't want to be restricted by the present. If participants want a future date, take one that is sufficiently far out, e.g., 2040 or 2050.

If people want to talk about problems or solutions in the present, kindly remind them that we will get there in the second half of the workshop. You can also encourage them to already write their thoughts down on a sticky note and park them on the top left quadrant.

- (10 Min) Joint sense-making. Discuss: What do people's desired connections with the lake have in common? What values are showing up again and again? Are there tensions?

Encourage participants to cluster the sticky notes. “As you cluster sticky notes, look for emerging themes or values that could represent a shared direction — even if not everyone expressed them the same way.”

- (5 Min) Let group decide on a group name. Try to let it reflect part of the following: what, where, who, until when. Capture the group name on a sticky-note. (possible input for graphic facilitator)
- (5 Min) Let the group capture the essence of their vision in a vision statement, future news headline, a 2-sentence social media post, or other expression. Can be multiple. Capture them on a paper. (possible input for graphic facilitator)

Joint lunch (12.10 – 50 minutes)

- Preferably a moment outside to get fresh air and connect with the lake

Step 3 - Populating the X-curve - What needs to grow (13:00 – 60 min)

Continue in subgroups.

Position in X-curve: Bottom left, working toward the middle — where early innovations, practices, and ideas begin to grow and influence change.

Objective: Identify promising seeds — local initiatives, practices, policies, or ideas — that align with your group’s future vision, and explore how these could grow, spread, or connect to shift systems toward that future.

- (5 min) Introduction by facilitator. Explain the X-curve’s bottom left as the space where promising alternatives begin, which are often informal, experimental, or marginal. These ‘seeds’ may be small now but hold transformative potential. Many reflect relational values — care, reciprocity, belonging, connection — even if they’re not always labelled as such.
- (10 min) Silent individual brainstorm. “What local initiatives, practices, cultural traditions, or policy ideas do you know that reflect the values in your group’s vision? Which ones could support movement toward that future?”

Each participant writes 2–3 ideas on sticky notes or cards. Encourage diversity: Existing formal or informal practices; Cultural or artistic expressions; Policy changes, behaviours, or technologies; Personal or community actions

- (20 min) Group sharing and mapping. Discuss what themes or domains can be identified. Which parts of the vision do they contribute to? What values are embodied? What makes them transformative? Are synergies emerging?
- (5 min) Jointly decide on 2 or 3 'seeds' to spotlight (possible input for graphic facilitator)
- (20 min) Early pathway thinking. What needs to happen for these initiatives to grow or spread? Who needs to be involved? What enabling conditions are needed (e.g. funding, policy change, narrative shifts)? What needs to shift — in values, policies, institutions, or behaviours? What needs to happen in the short term, what can happen later?

Coffee Break - 14.00 (20 min)

Step 4 - Populating the X-curve – Confronting Drivers, Enabling Futures (14.20 - 40 min).

Position in the X-curve: Middle. Following the trajectory from bottom left to top right, we explore how growing seeds must navigate and engage with the dominant forces that sustain the present (top left) and help shift or displace the patterns that need to decline (bottom right).

Objective: To explore how promising seeds of change can grow into transformative forces by actively engaging with, influencing, or helping to shift dominant drivers and structures that currently shape unsustainable trajectories.

- (5 min) Introduction by facilitator. We are now in the middle zone of the X-curve — the dynamic space where emerging seeds and practices begin to engage with the dominant systems that still shape the present. This is where transformation becomes strategic: it's no longer just about imagining alternatives, but about actively influencing or shifting key drivers, norms, and structures that currently sustain unsustainable trajectories (top left). This step asks: *What must these 'seeds' push against, navigate, or help transform for the futures we imagined to become possible?*

- (10 min) Group brainstorm: Identifying dominant forces. *“What dominant drivers, structures, behaviours, or narratives must these ‘seeds’ engage with for the desired future to become possible?”* Place them in the top left quadrant of the X-curve.
 - (15 min) Group brainstorm: How might the ‘seeds’ shift them? *“How could the ‘seeds’ help shift or transform the dominant forces to overcome tension and facilitate change?”* Place them in the centre.
 - (2–3 min) Closing with Agency: *“What is one **action** you feel inspired to contribute to — or one way you or your organisation might support transformation?”*
 - (5-min) Discuss a few highlights from the vision and pathway to share briefly in plenary. Decide who will do so.
-

Wrap-up discussion and next steps 15.00 (30 min)

- Each group reports back, focusing on a few key insights (2-3 min per group)
- Invite participants who want to share a final reflection or takeaway. (8 min)
- Explain next steps and how workshop outcomes will be used. (2 min)
- Closing words from workshop host(s) (2 min)
- Invite participation in follow-up and post-workshop survey. (2 min)

Meeting close (15.30)

6. Post-workshop processing and follow-up

Data collection

- Take photos of all outputs.
- Collect X-curve sheets with sticky notes from each group.
- Compile and organize notes from each group.
- Digitize each of the sticky notes, using rapporteur notes to support interpretation where needed

Data processing and analysis

- Assess participant feedback gathered through post-workshop survey results (Appendix I).
 - Reflect on what worked well and what could be improved for future workshops (e.g., in future visioning workshops, in the pathways workshops, etc.).
- Organize digitized sticky notes for easier analysis.
 - A helpful strategy for organizing sticky notes for analysis was developed by Heather Moorhouse. This strategy involves creating an Excel file and organizing sticky notes according to (i) group name and (ii) themes within the sticky notes for each step in the workshop, with each stage of the workshop included as separate sheets, i.e., one sheet for Group Names and Headlines, one for Visions, one for Dominant Norms/Practices that need to be phased out, one for Seeds of Change, and one for Navigating change/transformation. See Appendix II for an example setup.
 - This method of organizing data enables analysis of research questions (within and across case studies), such as: Are there descriptions or characteristics common to future visions across the groups? Are there dominant practices/norms or seeds of change that show up several times? Where do we see plural values arising? Etc.

Outputs and follow-up

- Using the compiled notes and digitized sticky notes, create a short workshop report to send to participants. This report can summarize the visions described by each group and compare where similarities and difference arose across groups.
 - See [Moorhouse et al., \(2025\)](#) for the report written on the visioning workshop held in the UK in May, 2025.
 - Share this report across the team for discussion and back to workshop participants for optional feedback.
- The rapporteur notes and sticky notes can also be used to translate descriptions of future visions into narratives (e.g., as stories). At subsequent workshops in these case studies, these narratives can then be presented back to participants to support the co-design of pathways towards achieving these visions.

7. References

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8. Appendix I: Post-workshop survey

PLURALAKES Post-Workshop Survey

Reflections on Participatory Visioning for Lake District Futures

Consent to Participate

Thank you for taking part in the PLURALAKES participatory visioning workshop. This short survey invites you to share reflections on your experience and your views on the topics discussed. Your responses will help us improve future workshops and contribute to research on integrating diverse values into lake governance.

Participation is voluntary and your answers will be stored securely, analyzed anonymously, and shared only in aggregated or anonymized form. Identifiable information will only be collected with your consent and used solely for follow-up communication.

By completing this survey, you consent to your responses being used for these purposes.

I agree to participate in this survey (Required to continue)

Section 1: Workshop Experience

(Likert scale: Strongly disagree – Disagree – Neutral – Agree – Strongly agree)

1. The workshop created a safe and respectful environment for discussion.
 2. The participatory activities helped me reflect on my values and connections to the lakes.
 3. The workshop methods were engaging and effective.
 4. Diverse perspectives were welcomed and valued.
 5. I feel more confident discussing or influencing the future of the Lake District's lakes
-

Section 2: Reflections on Outcomes and Change

(Open text responses)

6. What was the most valuable part of the workshop for you?
7. What could be improved in future workshops?
8. What inspired you to participate in this workshop?
9. Were there any important perspectives, voices, or issues you feel were missing from the discussions?
10. What would be good use of the workshop outcomes for you?
11. Do you have any wishes or ideas for follow-up workshops or next research steps in the PLURALAKES project?
12. Do you have any other reflections that you like to share?

Section 4: Staying Connected

13. Are you happy to continue be part of the process?

Yes

No

Privacy Notice

- This survey is conducted by [Institution] as part of the PLURALAKES project, funded by [Funder].
 - Responses will be processed for research, reporting, and improvement of workshop methods, and stored securely in accordance with GDPR.
 - Identifiable data will only be used with consent and for follow-up communication.
 - Data will be retained for up to [X years] and then securely deleted.
 - You have the right to withdraw, access, and request deletion of your data at any time.
 - For questions, contact [Research Lead + Email] or the Data Protection Officer at [Institution + DPO Email].
-

Thank You

Thank you for your valuable reflections. Your input will help shape inclusive, participatory approaches to supporting thriving lakes and communities in the Lake District.

9. Appendix II: Data organization example

Table I: Example set-up in Excel to organize sticky notes collected during the X-curve activity described in this Visioning Workshop Facilitation guide. The table provided below would be on one sheet that is specific to a step in the workshop process described here (e.g., description of future visions). The information provided on the sticky notes would be filled into the empty cells as a list, according to the group that wrote them and the theme they fit within. This example was provided by Heather Moorhouse.

Group	Theme 1 (e.g., description of ecosystem)	Theme 2 (e.g., attitudes and behaviours)	Theme 3 (e.g., governance)
Nature for Nature			
Nature as Culture			
Nature for Society			